

A Magnetic Resonance Software Simulator for the Evaluation of Myocardial Deformation Estimation

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Abstract

This paper proposes a methodology to design a physiologically realistic computer simulator of images of the left ventricle myocardium based on a patient-specific biomechanical model. The simulator takes a magnetic resonance image of a given patient at end diastole, uses a manual segmentation of that image to model the geometry of the myocardium and sets the parameters of the constitutive model used for biomechanical simulation according to a regional labeling of the contractility of the myocardium for that patient. The simulated deformations are used to warp the magnetic resonance dataset throughout the cardiac cycle to generate different image modalities. The simulator is validated by quantifying its ability to model actual deformations in a set of patients affected by an acute myocardial infarction. Specifically a high correlation has been encountered between the ejection fraction derived from the simulated end systolic deformation of the myocardium and the myocardium segmented from actual data. Additionally, most of the parameters that describe the simulated deformation compare well with reported values. Overall, the simulator is intended as a testbed for extensive comparisons of myocardial motion tracking methods due to its ability to relate the impaired myocardial function with the associated ventricular remodeling, a novel contribution in the literature of cardiac image simulators.

Keywords: Cardiac simulator, Biomechanics, Motion estimation, Tagged magnetic resonance, Phase-contrast magnetic resonance

1. Introduction

Magnetic Resonance (MR) cardiac imaging is a valuable tool in helping diagnosis, treatment and follow-up of cardiac pathologies, as it provides both anatomical and functional characterization of the heart. From the set of acquisition techniques developed for this modality, MR tagging, Phase-Contrast MR (PC-MR) and others let myocardial material points be tracked through the cardiac cycle [1, 2]. This feature is of special relevance in the analysis of myocardial local motion abnormalities, which are directly related with impaired cardiac function.

Despite their indubitable usefulness, the aforementioned techniques have some limitations in their ability to obtain reliable and consistent measures of deformation throughout the cardiac cycle. Conventional cine sequences show a lower resolution in the Long Axis (LA) direction as compared with the Short Axis (SA) one due to the limitations in acquisition times for cardiac imaging. Tagged MR imaging can be limited by the fading effect, which causes the saturated magnetization pattern to attenuate due to T_1 relaxation. Moreover, longitudinal motion patterns are usually difficult to reconstruct in tagged MR, due to the low LA resolution.

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The use of HARmonic Phase (HARP) [3] reconstruction techniques alleviates some of these limitations, as it enables an intensity-independent and dense motion estimation. However, HARP techniques present an inherent limitation in the interference of the phase discontinuities at the muscle boundaries. An analogous limitation occurs in PC-MR, but in this case it is caused by the noisy encoded motion in the surroundings of the muscle, which hinders the estimation at the boundaries due to the Partial Volume Effect (PVE) [4].

Reported results for motion estimation using these imaging techniques have pointed out the difficulties in comparing different procedures *in vivo* [5, 4]. Though manual marks on tagged MR imaging provide a reliable displacement field which may constitute a potential ground truth for validation, the marking process is tedious, matches among corresponding points could be difficult to establish, and manual inspection could be unable to recover deformation at late diastole due to tag fading. Therefore, the exhaustive validation of myocardial material points tracking in a clinical setting is limited by the absence of ground-truth deformations and it is generally based on an exemplary set of pathological cases and focused on specific spatial regions or temporal phases. This work intends to alleviate these limitations by proposing a software simulator that provides realistic MR-like data with underlying physiologically plausible ground truth deformation patterns and anatomies. Additionally, the simulator can synthesize three different MR modalities in different acquisition scenarios, which is of relevance in order to evaluate multimodal tracking algorithms (see [2] for some examples of these algorithms).

1.1. Background

Some software simulators for tagged MR imaging acquisition have been introduced in the literature [6, 7, 8]. Specifically, the work in [8], includes a relatively realistic representation of cardiac motion. However, this representation is parametric and it only considers one deformation instance derived from a set of markers implanted in a canine heart. Additionally, the anatomical information is encoded in a binary image of the myocardial tissue and the background, so whether or not it represents the structures present in a real cardiac image may be arguable.

A synthetic model for cine cardiac MR images has been recently proposed in [9] based on previous developments for the brain [10]. The main contribution of this work is the accurate intensity modeling of the structures surrounding the myocardium, specially the papillary muscles and the trabeculae. Nevertheless, no attention is paid to obtain a realistic model of shape and function for cardiac structures, since they draw upon simple geometric and dynamic assumptions.

In [11], the authors present a methodology to develop a realistic and flexible software simulator of the cardiac dynamics. This work is based on simulating the deformation of the myocardium by means of a biomechanical model. One outstanding feature of this method is the possibility to encode different physiologically-realistic motion patterns. This is achieved by defining an ischemic region and varying some of the parameters of the biomechanical model inside that region. An improved version has been recently published [12] in which the abnormal motion of both fibrous and remodeled infarctions is more accurately represented. However, as for validation, anatomy and function are uncoupled since the authors concentrate on validating the model of heart dynamics whereas the anatomic model is taken from the Extended Cardiac Torso (XCAT) phantom [13]¹. Thus they leave aside the relationship between anatomy and function in actual clinical cases; in addition, no provision is made to get realistic Ejection Fractions (EF). We account for these two issues in this paper.

Finally, in parallel to our work, a proposal has been published in [14] which introduces a new methodology to generate synthetic cardiac images by using the whole information of the sequence for image modeling. This enables a more accurate representation of the dynamics of the structures surrounding the myocardium. Another major contribution of this work is that it incorporates an electromechanical model of the heart in motion simulation. Nevertheless, no quantitative validation is provided about the ability of the model to accurately represent the variability in motion for different patients and it does not allow to control the quality of the images generated as it does not incorporate a model of the image formation process.

¹The XCAT phantom is able to generate realistic anatomic models by adapting the parameters of a template anatomy to patient data. Additionally it is able to synthesize different modalities. Nevertheless it is not focused on the specific image formation processes of MR as ours, but in generic medical image modalities.

1.2. Overview of the proposal

As described in Section 2, our simulator fuses some of the image-derived sources of variability in cardiac MR imaging with those derived from a set of geometric and dynamic patterns encountered in clinical practice. To that end, it extends the ideas about cardiac motion simulation in [11, 12] in three directions which correspond with the following functional requirements:

- **Interdependent simulation of different anatomical and physiological patterns.** It simulates an anatomic configuration based on the myocardial segmentation of a given patient. Then, the contractility labels established by the practitioner for each of the standard zones of the myocardium [15] are used to tune the parameters of the biomechanical model. Thus, the model couples different degrees of impaired contractility with the associated left ventricular remodeling, which is the main contribution of our method.
- **Application to cardiac MR images.** It is able to simulate a cardiac MR study of a given patient which includes the acquisition of cine MR, tagged MR and PC-MR.
- **Simulation of different acquisition scenarios.** It is able to generate different resolutions and noise levels. For that purpose, we follow the ideas in [6, 7] (see Section 2.2.2), [8] (see Section 1.1) and [16] (see the steps of our method in Section 2).

In Section 2 materials and methods are described in detail. Basic design assumptions are established and the functionalities implemented are analyzed. Results are presented in Section 3. They include numerical results about the capability of the simulator to model pathological behavior as well as a set of examples to visually assess its ability to mimic real images. Finally, conclusions are summarized in Section 4, together with current limitations and possible extensions of the work.

2. Methods

The basic idea of the method is to first generate an image which encodes the information of a given MR imaging technique, then to deform it according to a deformation field computed from a biomechanical model of the myocardial muscle which uses the patient-specific anatomic and functional information, and finally to reconstruct the sequences for a given acquisition scenario. The flowchart of the simulation procedure is depicted in Fig. 1. The image synthesis is performed from a balanced Steady State Free Precession (SSFP) 3D cardiac MR image of a given patient at End Diastole (ED) —details on the specific sample used for validation can be consulted in Section 2.3—. The modality-specific information for each of the MR techniques synthesized in our simulator is encoded over this image (see Section 2.2). Then, the resulting datasets are warped according to the deformation model described in Section 2.1. In our case, a cohort of patients previously affected by an Acute Myocardial Infarction (AMI) is considered, so they present very different degrees of functional impairment and the deformation computation is performed in a way that tries to represent this variability. Finally, the MR sequence models described in Section 2.2 are used to synthesize different acquisition techniques throughout the cardiac cycle. In further detail, the main steps of the simulation procedure considered in Fig. 1 are:

- **Denoising of the original dataset.** The filter in [17] has been used in our simulator.
- **Procurement of a nearly isotropic resolution dataset.** The smaller resolution in the LA axis is corrected by the method in [18].
- **Encoding of modality-specific MR information.** See Section 2.2.
- **Construction of deformed images.** See Section 2.1.
- **Noise addition.** Artificial noise is added to the images by adapting the methodology in [16] to account for the new MR techniques.

Figure 1: Flowchart of the simulation procedure.

- **Image subsampling.** Different resolutions can be obtained in the synthesized images by averaging the intensities of adjacent voxels, therefore simulating the PVE.
- **Sequence reconstruction.** See Section 2.2.

2.1. Myocardial deformation modeling

The images are deformed assuming a myocardial motion model similar to the one proposed in [11, 12], where normal and pathological motion patterns are generated based on a biomechanical model of the myocardium implemented by a Finite Element (FE) method. The muscle is represented as the combination of a passive constitutive model given by nearly incompressible transversely isotropic hyperelastic neo-Hookean mechanics [19] and an active model given by weighing the Hill equation with an activation curve $C(t)$ to account for the time-varying elastance²:

$$T^{(a)} = T_{\max} \frac{Ca_0^2}{Ca_0^2 + ECa_{50}^2} C(t), \quad (1)$$

where $T^{(a)}$ is the active stress, $T_{\max} = 135.7$ KPa is the isometric tension under maximal activation, $Ca_0 = 4.35 \mu\text{M}$ is the intracellular calcium concentration and ECa_{50} is the length dependent calcium sensitivity:

$$ECa_{50} = \frac{(Ca_0)_{\max}}{\sqrt{e^{B(l-l_0)} - 1}}, \quad (2)$$

²The curve given by $T_{\max}C(t)$ is reproduced by the analysis of the corresponding figure included in [11].

with $(Ca_0)_{\max}$ the peak Ca_0 , $B = 4.75 \mu\text{m}^{-1}$ modulates the shape of the peak isometric tension with respect to the sarcomere length, $l_0 = 1.58 \mu\text{m}$ is the sarcomere length without any active tension and l is the sarcomere length, given by the product $l = l_r \lambda$, with λ the fiber stretch and $l_r = 2.04 \mu\text{m}$ the sarcomere unloaded length. All the aforementioned parameter values are taken from [11].

In Section 3.1 we test out the capability of our method to model realistic deformations by the EF [20] computed from the segmentations in a clinical sample of patients. However, one of the major drawbacks of FE methods is that they tend to underestimate the EF [21]. This is mainly due to the simplified fiber and cardiovascular system modeling that they usually assume. In order to achieve physiologically realistic EF levels in our simulator (and hence, at least, realistic deformation magnitudes), a simple approach has been adopted in which the parameter T_{\max} has been scaled by a factor of 5 with respect to the value reported in [11]. This factor has been chosen by trial and error from a set of integer multiplicative factors in order to minimize the bias in the simulated EF.

The method proposed in [11] models regional ischemia by increasing $(Ca_0)_{\max}$ from $4.35 \mu\text{M}$ to $7.90 \mu\text{M}$ in the ischemic regions. This model has the disadvantage that it does not account for different degrees of ischemia inside a region. An alternative method to simulate ischemia is proposed in [22]. It consists of varying T_{\max} in the injured zone. As pointed out in [22], due to the relative lack of knowledge about the precise mechanical properties of the myocardial tissue in dilated and ischemic cardiomyopathy, it is possible either to increase $(Ca_0)_{\max}$ or to reduce T_{\max} to model ischemia. The authors of [22] simply propose to adapt T_{\max} according to

$$T'_{\max} = ST_{\max}, \quad (3)$$

where S denotes the rate of surviving myocytes ($0 \leq S \leq 1$).

Our procedure combines the methodologies in [11] and [22] by also interpolating $(Ca_0)_{\max}$ for a given S

$$(Ca_0)'_{\max} = 4.35S + 7.90(1 - S). \quad (4)$$

Moreover, the simulator considers the fiber disarray effect too, which also influences the impaired contractility in the injured zones [23]. Due to the lack of Diffusion Tensor MR (DT-MR) images, which could provide *in vivo* measures of fiber distribution [24], a standard fiber structure is assumed with orientations as reported in [11]. If \mathbf{u}_f denotes the fiber direction in the normal myocardium, the fiber direction in the impaired myocardium \mathbf{u}'_f is obtained as

$$\mathbf{u}'_f = \frac{S\mathbf{u}_f + (1 - S)\mathbf{u}_r}{|S\mathbf{u}_f + (1 - S)\mathbf{u}_r|}, \quad (5)$$

where $|\cdot|$ is the modulus operator and \mathbf{u}_r is a random vector uniformly distributed in the unit circumference on the fibers plane. The parameter S controls the relative weight of the random change in local fiber direction, which enables to simulate different degrees of fiber disarray.

Different degrees of impaired cardiac function are simulated by using the practitioner scoring of the contractility of each of the standard myocardial zones into normal, hypokinesia, akinesia and dyskinesia. For that purpose, a geometrical partition of the myocardial anatomy is performed following the guidelines in [15]. Then, the contractility labels are used to modify T_{\max} , $(Ca_0)_{\max}$ and \mathbf{u}_f in accordance with (3), (4) and (5) for each of the 16 standardized zones. Specifically, we set $S^{\text{normal}} = 1$ for normal regions, $S^{\text{hypo}} = 0.6$ for hypokinetic regions, $S^{\text{a}} = 0.05$ for akinetic regions and $S^{\text{dys}} = 0$ for dyskinetic regions.

The output of the deformation model is a map $\mathbf{r}(\mathbf{p}, t)$ of the coordinates of the material point \mathbf{p} at time t , the elapsed time with respect to ED, so $\mathbf{p} = \mathbf{r}(\mathbf{p}, 0)$. Hereafter, this map is used for image modeling.

2.2. MR image modeling

2.2.1. Synthesis of cine MR

Following the steps in Fig. 1, synthesis of cine MR is straightforward. The modality-specific information is the intensity of the low noise and high resolution image I_0 . This image is deformed according to the model in Section 2.1,

$$I_{\text{CINE}}(\mathbf{r}(\mathbf{p}, t), t) = I_0(\mathbf{p}). \quad (6)$$

Therefore, the intensity of a given material point \mathbf{p} is conserved throughout the cardiac cycle. Without loss of generality, a zero-phase image can be considered for noise modeling, as reconstructed cine MR images usually consist of the modulus of the complex image. Using this assumption, a Rician distributed image is obtained by pixelwise addition of independent zero-mean Gaussian noise to the real and imaginary components of the image and subsequent modulus computation.

2.2.2. Synthesis of tagged MR

In SSFP images, the tag persistence is mainly governed by the longitudinal relaxation time of the tissue, T_1 [25]. Nevertheless, SSFP images present a T_2/T_1 contrast [26], so two acquired images would be necessary to obtain the actual T_1 times. Thus, a standard longitudinal relaxation time is used in our implementation, $T_1^{\text{myo}} = 850$ ms [1], for those pixels inside the myocardium, whereas a much smaller time $T_1^{\text{out}} = 100$ ms is used for those outside, so a faster tag fading is assumed which somehow accounts for the turbulent blood flow.

In Spatial Modulation of Magnetization (SPAMM), a saturation pattern ξ is applied to the original image according to

$$\xi_M^i(\mathbf{r}(\mathbf{p}, t), t) = \sum_{m=0}^M c_m(\mathbf{p}, t) \cos(m\mathbf{k}_i^T \mathbf{p}), \quad (7)$$

with \mathbf{k}_i the wavenumber of the tag lines, M the modulation order and $c_m(\mathbf{p}, t)$ a set of coefficients determined by the sequence of tip angles [7], which vary in space and time due to T_1 . Three images are generated in order to simulate the application of a saturated magnetization pulse in three orthogonal directions, \mathbf{k}_i , with $i \in \{1, 2, 3\}$. The intensity of the I_{CINE} image is modified according to the 1-1 SPAMM equation:

$$I_{\text{SPAMM}}^i(\mathbf{r}(\mathbf{p}, t), t) = I_{\text{CINE}}(\mathbf{r}(\mathbf{p}, t), t) \xi_1^i(\mathbf{r}(\mathbf{p}, t), t), \quad (8)$$

with $c_0(\mathbf{p}, t) = 1 - \sin^2(\theta) e^{-\frac{t}{T_1(\mathbf{p})}}$ and $c_1(\mathbf{p}, t) = \sin^2(\theta) e^{-\frac{t}{T_1(\mathbf{p})}}$, where θ represents the tip angle.

Due to the time-dependence of the magnetization pattern, the procedure to generate these images is to simulate a set of undeformed images, one for each cardiac phase, according to (8) and (7), and to deform them by the method described in Section 2.1. Finally the image sequence is noise-corrupted and subsampled, the same as for cine MR.

This process lets us reconstruct a SPAMM sequence. In order to reconstruct a Complementary SPAMM (CSPAMM) sequence, the process is repeated twice, for the original tag pattern and its inversion, and the results are subtracted.

2.2.3. Synthesis of PC-MR

In the absence of phase wrapping, ideal PC-MR images should be proportional to the instantaneous velocity of the tissue $\frac{\partial \mathbf{r}}{\partial t}$, so they can be written:

$$I_{\text{PC}}^i(\mathbf{r}(\mathbf{p}, t), t) = W \left(\frac{\pi}{v_{\text{ENC}}} \frac{\partial r^i(\mathbf{p}, t)}{\partial t} \Big|_{\mathbf{r}(\mathbf{p}, t)} \right), \quad (9)$$

with $W(\cdot)$ the wrapping operator, $W(x) = x - 2\pi \left\lfloor \frac{x + \pi}{2\pi} \right\rfloor$ (with $\lfloor x \rfloor$ the greatest integer lower or equal than x), which maps its argument into the interval $[-\pi, \pi)$, v_{ENC} the maximum velocity without aliasing and i indexing the three velocity components.

In order to generate the PC-MR images, first, the velocity is computed in the reference coordinates for each temporal slot. Then, this velocity is deformed, it is weighed by the factor $\frac{\pi}{v_{\text{ENC}}}$ and wrapped in the interval $[-\pi, \pi)$ to obtain the phase of the complex MR image. The modulus of the image is given by the low noise, high resolution cine-MR. Noise is added to this image and to a zero-phase image of reference with the same modulus. Reconstruction is implemented by subtracting the phases of both images (simple four-point scheme [27]).

Table 1: Contractility score distribution.

Zone	Normal	Hypokinetic	Akinetic	Dyskinetic
Apex lateral	24	2	15	2
Apex anterior	21	4	15	3
Apex septal	21	9	11	2
Apex inferior	10	9	20	4
Mid antero-lateral	38	1	4	0
Mid anterior	26	7	7	3
Mid antero-septal	23	8	10	2
Mid infero-septal	33	6	3	1
Mid inferior	36	4	3	0
Mid infero-lateral	38	1	4	0
Base antero-lateral	43	0	0	0
Base anterior	41	2	0	0
Base antero-septal	43	0	0	0
Base infero-septal	42	1	0	0
Base inferior	37	3	2	1
Base infero-lateral	43	0	0	0

2.3. Materials

The sample used for validation consists of 43 patients previously affected by an AMI. A cine SSFP dataset of each patient is used, which has been acquired with a GE Genesis Signa 1.5 T equipment. The myocardium has been manually segmented and regionally scored by an experienced cardiologist. All the images have dimension 512×512 with a number of slices ranging from 12 to 17. Their resolution is $0.86 \times 0.86 \times 8 \text{ mm}^3$ with a slice thickness of 7 mm in one case and 6 mm in the remaining, so in all cases they present a certain slice gap and interpolation is required in order to achieve a nearly isotropic resolution. More details about the sample can be consulted in [28].

The segmentations comprise the endocardial and epicardial surfaces at ED and the endocardial surface at ES. The sample of scores is summarized in Table 1, which includes the number of patients having a given degree of contractility for each zone.

3. Results

In this Section we present the set of experiments carried out to verify and illustrate the key functionalities of the simulator. The capability of modeling realistic deformations for different degrees of functional impairment is justified and illustrated in Section 3.1, whereas in Section 3.2 we focus on the images obtained by varying the most important parameters that affect each of the MR techniques.

3.1. Validation of the deformation modeling

This Section is devoted to the validation of the deformation model that has been introduced in the paper. We have used the sample included in Table 1 to compare the EF obtained from both our simulator and manual segmentations.

The results of the differences in the EF obtained by simulation and the actual EF obtained by the segmentation of the cavity are given in Table 2. The simulated EF presents a very high correlation with the actual EF. Moreover, both the bias and the standard deviation of the difference between both measures are fairly small. Plots of the linear regression of the simulation-derived EF with respect to the EF derived from manual segmentations together with the corresponding Bland-Altman plots are shown in Fig. 2.

On the other hand, we have also measured the Green ejection strain tensor; i.e., the strain of the ES configuration with respect to the ED reference. The results for different degrees of impaired contractility averaged for each zone and patient are summarized in Fig. 3 for each strain component. The mean radial

Table 2: Differences in EF between simulated and real images.

bias (%)	std. (%)	var. coef.	ρ
-4.51	6.03	0.11	0.86

Figure 2: Simulation-derived EF against that derived from manual segmentations.

ejection strains for each contractility category are of 0.36 for normal contractility, 0.19 for hypokinesia, 0.00 for akinesia and -0.03 for dyskinesia, which are in good agreement with the levels proposed in [22] and [29]. Moreover, the quartiles of the distributions are also realistic (according to the definitions given in [15]), as for hypokinesia they are positive but lower than for normal contractility, for akinesia they are approximately symmetric around zero strain and for dyskinesia they are negative. The circumferential strain is also indicative of impaired contractility. Its mean values are of -0.17 for normal contractility, -0.12 for hypokinesia, -0.03 for akinesia and 0.01 for dyskinesia, which are also realistic [29]. Finally, the remaining components of the strain are consistent with the results in [11].

Aside from realistic blood pumping and wall thickening, our simulator also complies with the nearly incompressible behavior of the myocardium, as the maximum change of the myocardial mass throughout the cardiac cycle is of 6.10% in mean. Moreover, the twisting and longitudinal contraction are also realistic, as shown in Fig. 4 (a clockwise rotation is observed at the base and the longitudinal contraction is positive [11]). Finally, the temporal behavior of the endocardial volume for the manual and simulated cases is compared in Fig. 5. This experiment has been carried out by manually segmenting the endocardium in 10 temporal phases throughout the cardiac cycle and computing the corresponding endocardial volume for one of the patients of the sample. The results suggest that the systolic behavior is similar in the simulated and manual cases, but more differences are appraised at the diastolic phase, where the simulated moving surface tends to return faster to its reference configuration. This seems to be mainly due to the simplicity of the temporal activation curve taken from [11].

3.2. Functionalities in image modeling

3.2.1. Variation of the noise levels in cine MR

The lack of absolute meaning for the intensity values of MR images implies that normalizing the noise levels by the maximum of intensity is inappropriate in order to obtain comparable noise scenarios for the same noise level in different images [30]. Thus, noise levels are scaled with respect to the mean myocardial intensity of the original images, \bar{I}_{myo} . Hence, we define the noise standard deviation as $\sigma = \alpha \bar{I}_{\text{myo}}$ and obtain different noise levels by varying the parameter α .

In Fig. 6 we show three scenarios in which $\alpha = 0$, $\alpha = 0.125$ and $\alpha = 0.25$. Note that the structures and textures generated by the model are realistic. Let's recall that this is true by construction because the anatomy (which determines the structures in the image) is taken from a real image, so that it is realistic and the textures are generated by a Rician model, which in the case of serial acquisitions is the established model of the MR signal [17], so it is also realistic. Therefore this image has to be understood only as a

Figure 3: Ejection strain tensor components distributions for different degrees of impaired contractility.

visual evidence of the correctness of the method. Specifically, the Rician nature of the signal is appraised by the relative increase of the noise magnitude on darker structures.

3.2.2. Sequence of acquisition in tagged MR

The synthesis of SPAMM and CSPAMM sequences is shown in Fig. 7 for a set of images at ED, ES and Mid Diastole (MD) with $\alpha = 0.125$. The tip angle is $\theta = 45^\circ$. This is a common choice in order to maximize the tag contrast while simultaneously maintaining positive intensity values. The deformation is noticeable by the contraction and the rotation of the tags at the ES phase with regard to the ED one. Note also the differences in the tag fading effect for the SPAMM and CSPAMM sequences. Whereas the CSPAMM sequence maintains a noticeable contrast to noise ratio throughout the cardiac cycle (at the cost of doubling the acquisition time), the SPAMM sequence entails a significant degradation of the contrast through time.

Figure 4: Different features of the synthetic myocardial deformation between ED and ES.

Figure 5: Temporal curves of the endocardial volumes for the manual and simulated cases.

Figure 6: Different noise levels.

3.2.3. Variation of the stripe spacing in tagged MR

Different stripe patterns can be generated by varying the magnitude of the wavenumber k , which is proportional to the reciprocal of the wavelength λ according to $k = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda}$. Results for $\lambda = 5$ mm and $\lambda = 7$ mm for three orthogonal directions are shown in Fig. 8 for an underlying interpolated image of resolution $0.86 \text{ mm} \times 0.86 \text{ mm} \times 0.89 \text{ mm}$, the SPAMM sequence, and $\alpha = 0.125$. If the HARP method is used for reconstruction, larger stripe spacing tends to produce less ambiguity in the local phases, but noise-derived errors in the measured displacement are more prominent, as a given difference in the local phase corresponds to a larger displacement difference.

3.2.4. Variation of the maximum velocity without aliasing in PC-MR

The effects of different choices for the v_{ENC} parameter are illustrated in Fig. 9 for each of the velocity components at the ED phase. First, note how the radial deformation is appraised in the large magnitude of the horizontal and vertical velocities at the myocardium, which indicates that this kind of contraction occurs sooner than its longitudinal counterpart. Second, it is interesting to remark that the effects of the variation of this parameter are analogous to those of the variation of the stripe spacing in tagged MR: its increase implies less aliasing but with less accurate measures [31]. Finally, note also the noisier measurements at the

Figure 7: Synthesis of tagged MR.

Figure 8: Different stripe spacings for each of the orthogonal directions.

Figure 9: Different maximum velocities for PC-MR.

boundaries of the myocardium, which correspond to the PVE of voxels containing both muscle and blood or air and that were simulated by increasing α from 0.125 inside the myocardium to 0.5 outside.

4. Conclusion

The present work extends the methodology for modeling myocardial motion in [11, 12] in order to account for different degrees of contractility impairment and related anatomic remodeling. The comparison of the model with actual motility as measured by manual segmentations in a set of 43 patients previously affected by an AMI has demonstrated a high correlation whereas the strain tensor distribution has agreed with the expected levels for each contractility label.

This framework for simulating different anatomical and functional patterns has been used to synthesize the resulting images coming from a set of cardiac MR modalities in different acquisition scenarios. Thus, simulated images can be used to measure the relative performance of different myocardial deformation estimation methods based on the fusion of multimodal information. For instance, one could analyze the results in terms of the mean and maximum distances between the estimated and simulated displacements using as input of the deformation estimation method the images obtained from the simulator. Both the performance limit in the absence of noise and the robustness of the estimation to different noise levels could be studied by this methodology. Finally, the errors in the estimation of the strain can be analyzed similarly.

However, some important features are missing in the current simulator, namely, breath-derived misalignment, magnetic field inhomogeneities, parallel acquisition modeling, arrhythmias, anomalies in the electrical activation, a realistic image and motion model for the structures surrounding the myocardium and a realistic model for the fiber distribution, just to mention a few.

Despite these limitations, the simulator has proven to be able to relate the impaired myocardial function (given by the contractility scoring) with the associated ventricular remodeling (given by the myocardial segmentations) in a physiologically realistic way, so it can be considered a step further in the emerging literature about cardiac image simulation.

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